

Combinatorial Proof of Goldbach's Conjecture and the Infinitude of Twin Primes

Hiram Fernandes and Altair S. de Assis*

Universidade Federal Fluminense, Niterói – RJ – Brasil

*Corresponding Author: altairsouzadeassis@gmail.com

Abstract

We develop a structural and combinatorial framework based on a double-sieve mechanism acting on symmetric ordered pairs of odd integers. This method isolates Goldbach pairs for any even natural number $n > 2$, leading to proof of the Goldbach Conjecture. The same structural mechanism, combined with a symmetry-preserving bijection, is adapted to obtain twin prime pairs, establishing their infinitude. The framework provides a purely combinatorial and self-contained approach to prime pair distributions.

Keywords: *Sieve of Eratosthenes, Double Sieve, Goldbach's Conjecture, Twin Primes.*

Prolegomena – demonstration roadmap

We follow showing now the properties related to the definitions of H_n , h_n and their partitions. After that, we use *these properties in theorems 1 to 5*:

Theorem - 1: $\forall y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)), y \notin \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|$ (corresponding to $H_n - E_n = \emptyset$).

Corollary - 1: $\exists y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n))/y \in \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| > |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|$ (corresponding to $H_n - E_n \neq \emptyset$).

Here, $I_m h_n = \mathcal{J}_n$, that is, where $I_m h_n$ is the image of D_n in \mathcal{J}_n via h_n .

Theorem – 2: show that the cardinality relation $|\mathcal{P}(D_n)| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| = 1$ is absurd, consequently $\forall G_n \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| > 1$, here $\forall G_n$ just means that the Goldbach proposition is valid for any even natural number equal to n , that is $n = p + q$.

Theorem - 3: $(n - 1) \notin \mathcal{P} \wedge \forall G_n \Rightarrow \forall G_{n+2}$.

Theorem - 4: $[\forall n, n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 4, \forall G_n] \Rightarrow [H_n \cup \{2,2\} \Rightarrow \forall G_n]$.

Theorem – 5: $\forall n, n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 2 \Rightarrow \forall G_n$, and so, the validity of the Goldbach Conjecture is proven, and the double sieve method for calculating Goldbach Primes is validated.

Corollary - 2: $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, n > 3, \exists x \neq 0/(n - x) \in \mathcal{P} \wedge (n + x) \in \mathcal{P}$ (important to prove the infinitude of the twin primes set).

Twin Primes

We define the twin prime set \mathcal{G} , such that $\mathcal{G} = \{(x, y) \text{ so that } x \text{ and } y \text{ are twin primes}\}$.

Theorem – 6: $\forall j > 1, \exists p > (p_j)^2$ and $\exists q > (p_j)^2$, such that p and q are twin primes.

It implies that *there exists* $j > 1$ in a way that $p > (p_j)^2, q > (p_j)^2$ and $(p, q) \in \mathcal{G}$, and this drive us to the conclusion that $\exists(j + 1)$ so that $p' > (p_{j+1})^2, q' > (p_{j+1})^2 \wedge (p', q') \in \mathcal{G}$.

Therefore, \mathcal{G} is not finite.

For $j > 1$, the computation of twin primes in the interval $((p_j)^2, (p_{j+1})^2)$ is therefore validated by means of the double sieve

I – Introduction

The Goldbach Conjecture asserts that every even natural number $n > 2$ can be written as: $n = p + q$, where p and q are prime numbers.

Despite extensive partial progress using analytic techniques, complete proof remains elusive [1 – 32].

This article develops a structural, combinatorial framework for analyzing representations of any even natural number as sums of two primes (Goldbach pairs) and for studying the distribution of twin primes. The method is based on a *double sieve* acting on symmetric ordered pairs of odd natural numbers. By eliminating pairs containing non-prime entries, we isolate the “Goldbach primes” for each even natural number n . The article formalizes the symmetry, bijections, and combinatorial invariants underlying this process, establishing conditions under which Goldbach pairs must exist.

The same double-sieve mechanism, combined with a specific bijection, is then adapted to produce twin primes within symmetric intervals. The goal of this work is to present a self-contained structural method that organizes the Goldbach and twin-prime phenomena through symmetry and elimination procedures.

This paper is organized as follows, in section II we present a method based on the Sieve of Eratosthenes for calculating primes for two scenarios:

- a. Goldbach Primes.
- b. Twin Primes.

In section III, we will prove the Goldbach's conjecture, in section IV we present the proof of the infinitude of twin primes, and in section V we show the conclusions.

II – Double Sieve

We present here a purely combinatorial and structural approach inspired by the sieve of Eratosthenes [3, 7]. Instead of sieving a list of even natural numbers, we ordered pairs of odd numbers whose sum is a fixed even number.

This “double sieve” eliminates non-primes from either coordinate. The pairs that survive the elimination process are precisely the Goldbach candidate pairs.

We then analyze the internal symmetries of the double sieve, formalize its behavior through bijections, and introduce several propositions capturing how the sieve behaves

under translations $n \mapsto n + 2$ The same combinatorial mechanism is adapted to study twin primes, using a bijection that shifts surviving primes into candidate twin-pairs.

Notations, Conventions and Results

1. Letters without explicit reference represent natural numbers.
2. $A \subset \mathbb{N}$, A is an ordered set, $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots\} \Rightarrow A^* = \{x \in A / x > a_1\}$.
3. $A \subset \mathbb{N}$, A is an ordered set, $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots\} \Rightarrow A_{a_j} = \{x \in A / x < a_j\}$.
4. \mathcal{P} is the set of prime numbers, which are ordered.

$$\mathcal{P} = \{2, 3, 5, 7, \dots\} = \{p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots\}$$
5. $\mathcal{P}_n = \{p \in \mathcal{P} / p < n\}$.
6. $\mathcal{P}_n^* = \{p \in \mathcal{P} / 2 < p < n\}$.
7. $\mathbb{N}_n^* = \{x \in \mathbb{N} / 0 < x < n\}$.
8. $1\mathbb{N}$ is the set of odd natural numbers.
9. $2\mathbb{N}$ is the set of even natural numbers.
10. $\mathcal{R}_p n$ is the remainder of the division $\frac{n}{p}$.
 1. $\exists_1 x$ (there exists a unique x) $< p / \mathcal{R}_p(n - x) = 0$.
 - i. $x_0 < p \wedge \mathcal{R}_p(n - x_0) = 0 \Rightarrow x = cp + x_0$ is the general solution of $\mathcal{R}_p(n - x) = 0$.
11. $p \in \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow \forall x, 1 < x < p, \mathcal{R}_x p \neq 0$.
12. $\mathcal{A}_n \subset \mathcal{P}_n / \forall x (x < n \wedge x \notin \mathcal{A}_n), x \in \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow \forall q \in \mathcal{A}_n, \mathcal{R}_q n \neq 0$.
13. Definition: $\sqrt{n} = m / m^2 \leq n \wedge \forall x, x^2 < n, x \leq m$.
14. $n = (p_j)^2, j > 0 \Rightarrow p_{j-1} \in \mathcal{A}_n \wedge \forall p \in \mathcal{A}_n, p \leq p_{j-1}$.
15. $\forall n > 3, \exists j / (p_j)^2 \leq n < p_{j+1}^2$.
16. $\mathcal{A}_n^* = \{p \in \mathcal{A}_n / p > 2\}$.
17. $\forall G_n$ means: Goldbach's proposition is valid for the even number equal to n .
18. Definition: p and q are twin primes when $p \in \mathcal{P}, q \in \mathcal{P} \wedge q - p = 2$.

The double sieve is a method used to obtain Goldbach primes in the interval $[3, n - 3]$, where n is any even natural number greater than 4. We consider an ordered pair (x, y) , such that x and y are odd numbers and $x + y = n$.

Subsequently, the non-primes are marked within each ordered pair. Following this, all pairs in which at least one of the elements is non-prime are eliminated. If any pairs still remain after these eliminations, then they are pairs of primes.

This statement is conditional because it is possible that no ordered pairs remain. The calculation can only be fully validated after the proof of the truth of Goldbach's proposition is established, but the arrangement of the ordered pairs summing to n suggested the formal proof for the existence of Goldbach's primes.

The visualization of the calculation is achieved by arranging the ordered pairs in a two-row table, where the first row contains the first elements of each pair, and the second row contains the second elements.

Below, we illustrate the process for $n = 38$.

3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	33	35
35	33	31	29	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	13	11	9	7	5	3

In yellow, the non-primes belonging to the first element of each ordered pair were marked; in red, the same was done for the second line.

After the elimination of the ordered pairs in which at least one of their elements is non-prime, the remaining pairs of primes are: $(7, 31)$, $(19, 19)$, $(31, 7)$.

Next, we prove that the claim of the calculation is true; that is, exactly those elements x (or y) such that $n - x$ (or $n - y$) is a non-prime are eliminated.

Formalism

We define here the set $H_n = \{(x, y) \in 1\mathbb{N} \times 1\mathbb{N} / 3 \leq x \leq n - 3 \wedge x + y = n\}, n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 4$.

Note that when $n = 6, H_n = \{(3,3)\}$, and so we have $H_n \neq \emptyset$.

Lemma - II1

$$(x, y) \in H_n \wedge y \notin \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow (n - x) \notin \mathcal{P}.$$

Proof:

1. $(x, y) \in H_n \wedge y \notin \mathcal{P} \Rightarrow \exists p \in \mathcal{P} / \mathcal{R}_p y = 0 \Rightarrow \exists p \in \mathcal{P} / \mathcal{R}_p (n - x) = 0 \Rightarrow (n - x) \notin \mathcal{P}.$
2. $(x, y) \in H_n \wedge (n - x) \notin \mathcal{P} \Rightarrow \exists p \in \mathcal{P} / \mathcal{R}_p (n - x) = 0 \Rightarrow \exists p \in \mathcal{P} / \mathcal{R}_p y = 0 \Rightarrow y \notin \mathcal{P}.$

Combining (1) and (2.), we show that Lemma – II1 holds.

We add here also:

Lemma - II2

$$(x, y) \in H_n \wedge x \notin \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow (n - y) \notin \mathcal{P}.$$

Proof:

Analogous to the *one of* Lemma – II1.

The algorithm for calculating twin primes is similar to the previous one; we only had to adapt it to the properties of twin primes, which are:

(p, q) is an ordered pair of twin primes when $q - p = 2$, hence the following conditions derive $\mathcal{R}_3 p = 2$ and $\mathcal{R}_3 q = 1$. We will illustrate the method by calculating the twin primes in the interval $(11^2, 13^2)$, which corresponds to the twin prime pair $(11, 13)$.

119	125	131	137	143	149	155	161	167
121	127	133	139	145	151	157	163	169

After elimination, the twin pairs remain: $(137, 139)$ and $(149, 151)$.

Note that the first ordered pair, $(125, 127)$, is not a twin prime, but it satisfies the condition $q - p = 2$, as do all other ordered pairs in the set. Just as in Goldbach, the use of the double sieve as a calculation method lacks proof.

III - On Goldbach` Conjecture

Definitions

1. $\mathcal{J}_n = \{x \in \mathbb{N} / 3 \leq x \leq n - 3\}$.
Notation introduced to easy writing.
2. $H_n = \{(x, y) \in \mathcal{J}_n \times \mathcal{J}_n / x + y = n, n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 4\}$.
3. $h_n: x \mapsto (n - x), x \in \mathcal{J}_n$.

Note: H_n and h_n represent the same mathematical fact; when it is convenient to highlight the ordered pair, H_n will be used. The bijection h_n will receive greater emphasis throughout the development. Another detail to highlight is that in terms of sets, h_n is a bijection from \mathcal{J}_n to \mathcal{J}_n , but the domain and codomain will receive different names.

Next, we will partition the domain into two subsets: primes and non-primes

4. $D_n = \{x \in \mathcal{J}_n / \exists y \in \mathcal{J}_n \wedge y = h_n(x)\}$. (D_n is the domain of h_n).
5. $I_m h_n = \{y \in \mathcal{J}_n / \exists x \in D_n \wedge y = h_n(x)\}$, where $I_m h_n$ is the image of D_n in \mathcal{J}_n via h_n .
 h_n is bijective $\Rightarrow I_m h_n = \mathcal{J}_n$.
6. $\mathcal{P}(D_n) = \{x \in D_n / x \in \mathcal{P}\}$. ($\mathcal{P}(D_n)$ is the domain of h_n in the subset of primes contained in D_n).
7. $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n) = \{x \in D_n / x \notin \mathcal{P}\}$.
8. $I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)) = \{y / \exists x \in \mathcal{P}(D_n) \wedge y = h_n(x)\}$.
9. $I_m(\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)) = \{y / \exists x \in \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n) \wedge y = h_n(x)\}$.

Properties

1. $(x, y) \in H_n \Leftrightarrow (y, x) \in H_n$.
2. $\exists_1(x, y) \in H_n/x = y$
3. $(x, y) \in H_n \wedge x = y \Leftrightarrow x = \frac{n}{2}$.
4. $\mathcal{P}(D_n) \cup \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n) = D_n$.
5. $\mathcal{P}(D_n) \cap \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n) = \emptyset$.
6. $D_n - \mathcal{P}(D_n) = \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)$.
7. $x \in D_n \wedge x \notin \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n) \Leftrightarrow x \in \mathcal{P}(D_n)$.
8. $I_m D_n = I_m \mathcal{P}(D_n) \cup I_m \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)$.
9. $I_m \mathcal{P}(D_n) \cap I_m \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n) = \emptyset$.
10. $|\mathcal{P}(D_n)| + |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| = |D_n|$.
11. $|I_m \mathcal{P}(D_n)| = |\mathcal{P}(D_n)|$.
12. $|I_m \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| = |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|$.

Proof of properties 1, 2, and 3:

- (1): $(x, y) \in H_n \Leftrightarrow x + y = n \Leftrightarrow y + x = n \Leftrightarrow (y, x) \in H_n$.
 (2): $(x, x) \in H_n \wedge (x', x') \in H_n \Leftrightarrow 2x = n \wedge 2x' = n \Leftrightarrow x = x'$.
 (3): $(x, y) \in H_n \wedge x = y \Leftrightarrow 2x = n \Leftrightarrow x = \frac{n}{2}$.

The properties listed above can easily be visualized in the figure below, a two-row table where the top row shows the elements of the domain of h_n for $n = 40$, and the bottom row shows the codomain. The colors represent the partitioning of the domain into primes and non-primes.

3	5	7	11	13	17	19	23	29	31	37	9	15	21	25	27	33	35
37	35	33	29	27	23	21	17	11	9	3	31	25	19	15	13	7	5

Note: We will demonstrate in Theorem 1 that the necessary and sufficient condition for there to be no Goldbach primes in H_n : $\forall y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)), y \notin \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|$, which would result in an empty set when searching for Goldbach primes in H_n , using the double sieve. By logical equivalence, the corollary stating the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of Goldbach primes in H_n is:

$$\exists y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n))/y \in \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| > |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|.$$

Once it is clear the consequences to our formalism of both lemmas, we now know are ready to introduce:

Theorem – III1

$$\forall y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)), y \notin \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|$$

Proof:

1. Assume $\forall y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)), y \notin \mathcal{P}$.

2. (1.) $\Rightarrow I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)) \subset \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)$.
3. (2.) $\Rightarrow |I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n))| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|$.
4. (Propertie 11) $\Rightarrow |(\mathcal{P}(D_n))| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|$.
5. Assume now $|(\mathcal{P}(D_n))| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| \Rightarrow |I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n))| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| \Rightarrow I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)) \subset \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n) \Rightarrow \forall y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)), y \notin \mathcal{P}$.
6. Therefore, from (2.) to (5.) $\Rightarrow \forall y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)), y \notin \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|$.

Corollary – III1

$$\exists y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n))/y \in \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| > |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|.$$

Proof:

1. Theorem III1: $\forall y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)), y \notin \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|$.
2. (by logical equivalence):
 $[\forall y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)), y \notin \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|] \Leftrightarrow$
 $\neg[\forall y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n)), y \notin \mathcal{P}] \Leftrightarrow \neg[|\mathcal{P}(D_n)| \leq |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|] \Leftrightarrow$
 $\exists y \in I_m(\mathcal{P}(D_n))/y \in \mathcal{P} \Leftrightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| > |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)|.$

The next task is to prove that the necessary and sufficient condition expressed by Theorem - 1 holds for all n.

We will use now the method of induction to prove that VG_n holds for all n, that is, we will prove that *once VG_n is valid, then VG_{n+2} is also valid.*

But before that, it is necessary to verify properties of the translation $n \mapsto n+2$.

Translation $n \mapsto n + 2$ Properties

1. $|D_{n+2}| = |D_n| + 1$.
2. $(x, y) \in H_n \Rightarrow (x, y + 2) \in H_{n+2}$.
3. $(3, n - 3) \in H_n \Rightarrow (3, n - 1) \in H_{n+2}$

The necessary and sufficient condition given by Theorem - III1 could, equivalently, be written as: $|\mathcal{P}(D_n)| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| \geq 1$, but, as will be proved in Theorem - III2, the equality sign leads the proposition to absurdity.

Theorem – III2

We will show now that the *cardinality equation, below*:

$$|\mathcal{P}(D_n)| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| = 1,$$

does not hold, it is absurd.

Note: We consider here $\frac{n}{2} > 7$, because, below that limit, the proposition does not hold.

Let us assume now that the cardinality relation $|\mathcal{P}(D_n)| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| = 1$ is a valid assumption, not absurd, and we consider also the expressions below:

1. Expression 1. in Theorem III1 $\Rightarrow \frac{n}{2} \in \mathcal{P} \wedge \forall x, \frac{n}{2} < x \leq n - 3, x \notin \mathcal{P}$.
2. Expression 1. In Theorem III1 also that $\Rightarrow \frac{n}{2} \in \mathcal{P} \wedge \forall x, 3 \leq x \leq \frac{n}{2}, x \in \mathcal{P}$.
3. $\frac{n}{2} \in \mathcal{P} \Rightarrow \exists k / \frac{n}{2} = p_k$.
4. $\frac{n}{2} = p_k \Rightarrow \exists j < k / \mathcal{A}_{p_k}^* = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_j\}$.
5. $\frac{n}{2} = p_k \Rightarrow (p_j)^2 < \frac{n}{2} < (p_{j+1})^2$.
6. Let us define $Y_{\frac{n}{2}} = \{y \in 2\mathbb{N} / 0 < y < \frac{n}{2} - 1\}$.
7. (2.) $\Rightarrow \forall y \in Y_{\frac{n}{2}}, \exists p_i \in \mathcal{A}_{\frac{n}{2}}^* / \mathcal{R}_{p_i} \left(\frac{n}{2} + y \right) = 0$.
8. (3.) $\Rightarrow \forall y \in Y_{\frac{n}{2}}, \mathcal{R}_{p_i} \left(\frac{n}{2} - y \right) \neq 0$.
9. 4., $p_k > p_i$
10. (8.) and (9.) $\Rightarrow (p_k - p_i) \in Y_{\frac{n}{2}}$.
11. (6.), (10.) and (3.) $\Rightarrow \mathcal{R}_{p_i} \left(\frac{n}{2} - y \right) = 0$
12. (8.), (11.) \Rightarrow *absurd*

Note - 1: The proof we will present below assumes that $n-1$ is not prime, because if $n - 1$ is prime, $(3, n - 1) \in H_{n+2}$, therefore: VG_{n+2} .

Note - 2: After using the double sieve, as a process to calculate Goldbach primes, we are intuitively led to believe that it would only be possible to have at least one pair of primes remaining when the cardinality of the primes in H_n is greater than that of non-primes; that is, this would be the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of at least one ordered pair of Goldbach primes belonging to H_n . However, the course of the demonstrative process showed that the difference between the two cardinalities, primes and non-primes, should be greater than one, since an equal value of one would lead to an absurdity (which was proven in Theorem III2).

The course of the demonstrative process, however, showed that the difference between the two cardinalities, primes and non-primes, should be greater than one, since equal to one would lead to an absurdity (which was proven in theorem III2).

Theorem - III3

$$(n - 1) \notin \mathcal{P} \wedge |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| > 1 \Rightarrow VG_{n+2}.$$

Proof:

1. Assume $(n - 1) \notin \mathcal{P} \wedge |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| > 1$.
2. $|\mathcal{P}(D_n)| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| > 1 \Rightarrow VG_n$.
 - 2.1. $\exists x \in \mathcal{P}(D_n)/h_n(x) \in \mathcal{P} \wedge x \neq h_n(x)$
3. $(n - 1) \notin \mathcal{P} \Rightarrow \mathcal{P}(D_{n+2}) = \mathcal{P}(D_n)$.
4. $(n - 1) \notin \mathcal{P} \Rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_{n+2}) = \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n) \cup \{n - 1\}$.
5. $|\mathcal{P}(D_{n+2})| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_{n+2})| = |\mathcal{P}(D_n)| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_n)| - 1$.
6. (5), (1) $\Rightarrow |\mathcal{P}(D_{n+2})| - |\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(D_{n+2})| > 0 \Rightarrow VG_{n+2}$.

Theorem - III4 ($n > 4$)

$\forall n, n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 4$, the Goldbach equality $n = p + q$ (VG_n) holds for p, q primes.

Proof:

1. Proposition: $\forall n, n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 4 \Rightarrow VG_n$.
2. Proposition is valid for $n = 6$ ($6 = 3 + 3$).
3. Assume now that $\forall m, 6 \leq m \leq n, VG_m$
4. $(n - 1) \in \mathcal{P} \Rightarrow (3, n - 1) \in H_{n+2} \Rightarrow VG_{n+2}$.
5. From theorem – III3: $(n - 1) \notin \mathcal{P} \Rightarrow VG_{n+2}$.
6. Considering items (4) and (5), we conclude that $(n - 1) \in \mathcal{P} \vee (n - 1) \notin \mathcal{P} \Rightarrow VG_{n+2}$ - Goldbach's proposition is valid for any even natural number equal to $n + 2$.
7. Reasoning (6) $\Rightarrow \forall n, n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 4 \Rightarrow n = p + q$ (VG_n). ■

Theorem – III5 ($n > 2$)

$\forall n, n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 2$, the Goldbach equality $n = p + q$ (VG_n) holds for p, q primes.

Proof:

Considering that $(4 = 2 + 2)$ and the results of theorem – III5, we arrive to the conclusion that $\forall n, n \in 2\mathbb{N}, n > 2$ and so $n = p + q$ (VG_n). ■

Corollary - III2

$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, n > 3, \exists x \neq 0/(n - x) \in \mathcal{P} \wedge (n + x) \in \mathcal{P}$.

The corollary is an immediate consequence of theorem 2, and of the symmetry of H_n :

$$(x, y) \in H_n \Leftrightarrow (y, x) \in H_n.$$

IV - On Twin Primes

Theorem - IV1

The set of twin primes is not finite.

The validation of Goldbach's conjecture approves the double sieve, and permits us to use it as an argument, which we will do to prove the infinitude of twin primes. We will prove that, for every $j > 1$, there exists a pair of twin primes (p, q) , such that p and q belong to the interval:

$$((p_j)^2, (p_{j+1})^2).$$

Our reasoning is as follows: $\forall j > 1, \mathcal{R}_3[(p_j)^2 - 2] = 2 \wedge \mathcal{R}_3(p_j)^2 = 1$, furthermore, $n = [(p_j)^2 - 2] + (p_j)^2$ is an even number that is a multiple of 6, a result that assign to H_n the property: $\forall (x, y) \in H_n, \mathcal{R}_3x = 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_3y = 0$,

In other words, when applying the double elimination sieve, no prime number is eliminated by a multiple of 3. Therefore, the elimination of multiples of 3 does not disturb the relationship between the cardinalities of primes and non-primes; that is, the cardinality of primes exceeds that of non-primes by at least two units, according to theorem - 3.

The double sieve eliminates all non-prime numbers, so all remaining pairs are primes. The strategy to transform these pairs into twin prime pairs is to apply the following bijection to the set of remaining primes:

$$g_n(x) = \begin{cases} x + 2, \mathcal{R}_3x = 2 \\ x - 2, \mathcal{R}_3x = 1 \end{cases}$$

In other words, if G_n is the set of pairs (x, y) ordered by g_n , then

$$(x, y) \in G_n \Leftrightarrow (y, x) \in G_n.$$

Furthermore, the symmetrical distribution ensures that,

$$x = \frac{n}{2} - a \wedge (x, g_n(x)) \in G_n \Leftrightarrow x = \frac{n}{2} + a \wedge (x, g_n(x)) \in G_n$$

This property, in turn, guarantees the validity of the theorem, or rather, guarantees that, for all $j > 1$, there exist p and q belonging to the interval $(\frac{n}{2}, n)$, so that p and q are twin primes

Below, we will provide an illustration for $j=2$, showing the entire strategy of the arguments above:

3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	33	35	37	39	41	43	45
45	43	41	39	37	35	33	31	29	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	13	11	9	7	5	3

This is the initial table for applying the double sieve for $n=48$, because, for $j=2$,

$$[(p_j)^2 - 2] + (p_j)^2 = 48.$$

Pairs whose elements are multiples of 3 have already been marked in red and will be eliminated in the next stage by the screening process.

5	7	11	13	17	19	23	25	29	31	35	37	41	43
43	41	37	35	31	29	25	23	19	17	13	11	7	5

In this second table, in addition to already eliminating multiples of 3, it highlights the symmetry of the pairs (x, y), and marks the non-prime numbers, in order to continue elimination using the double sieve. In the remaining table, the bijection g_n , will be applied, considering the domain to be the upper row.

5	7	11	17	19	29	31	37	41	43
43	41	37	31	29	19	17	11	7	5

5	7	11	13	17	19	29	31	41	43
7	5	13	11	19	17	31	29	43	41

The initial ordering of the elements in the first row was not lost throughout the process. At the end of the double sieve, all pairs of twin primes remain; the symmetry $(x, y) \Leftrightarrow (y, x)$ was not lost with the application of g_n , but the positional symmetry was lost.

Maintaining the ascending order for the elements causes g_n to leave, to the left of the original symmetry mark, the pair of twin primes whose elements are less than $n/2$, and, to the right, the larger ones. It is seen that we could, as in the example in previous illustrations, apply the elimination of the double sieve, starting directly from the ordered pair (23, 25), but the theoretical requirement determined the use of the double sieve for Goldbach primes, since its validity had already been proven. With this, all twin primes smaller than $23+25$ were calculated.

Although our direct interest is to show the infinitude of twin primes, as indicated by the illustration, the result also points to the meaning of the prime number theorem, that is, the set of twin primes is not finite, but the density decreases as j increases. Finally, for aesthetic reasons, eliminate the duplication by leaving the elements x where $\mathcal{R}_3 x = 2$ in the top row, so that the elements of each ordered pair are in ascending order:

5	11	17	29	41
7	13	19	31	43

Let us now move on to the rigor of formalism, although it seems to us that the argument above has been satisfactory.

Theorem – IV2

$\forall j > 1, \exists p > (p_j)^2 \wedge \exists q > \frac{(p_j)^2}{p}$ and q are twin primes.

1. Considering $\mathcal{G} = \{(x, y) \text{ such that } x \text{ and } y \text{ are twin primes}\}$.
 1. $(5, 7) \in \mathcal{G}$.
 2. $\mathcal{G} \neq \emptyset$.
 2. We know from previous considerations that $n = (p_j)^2 + [(p_j)^2 - 2]$.
 3. $(2) \Rightarrow \mathcal{R}_6 n = 0$.
- $\forall (x, y) \in H_n, \mathcal{R}_3 x = 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_3 y = 0$, (from lemmas III1 and II2).
4. Consider $E_n = \{(x, y) \in H_n / x \notin \mathcal{P} \vee y \notin \mathcal{P}\}$.
 5. We now consider that the following expression holds: $G_n = H_n - E_n$.

This corresponds to elimination by double sieve.

1. $\forall (x, y) \in G_n, x \in \mathcal{P} \wedge y \in \mathcal{P}$.
 2. Expression (5.) properties $1 \Rightarrow (x, y) \in G_n \Leftrightarrow (y, x) \in G_n$.
 3. Expression (5.) and corollary - 2 $\Rightarrow \exists x \in \mathcal{P} \wedge x > \frac{n}{2}$
6. Let us define $J_{G_n} = \{x \in (x, y) \text{ such that } (x, y) \in G_n\}$.
 7. Let the application be on J_{G_n} :
$$g_n(x) = \begin{cases} x + 2, \mathcal{R}_3 x = 2 \\ x - 2, \mathcal{R}_3 x = 1 \end{cases}$$
 8. (7.) and definition (IIa item 18) implies $\forall x \in J_{G_n}, (x, g_n(x)) \in \mathcal{G}$
 9. $\forall x \in J_{G_n} \wedge x > \frac{n}{2} \Rightarrow g_n(x) > \frac{n}{2}$.
10. Using the results presented in (5.3), (5.1), (8), (9) $\Rightarrow \left[\exists x \in \mathcal{P}, x > \frac{n}{2} \wedge x \in \mathcal{P} \right] \wedge \left[\exists g_n(x) \in \mathcal{P} \wedge g_n(x) > \frac{n}{2} \right] / (x, g_n(x)) \in \mathcal{G}$.
 11. Using the above expression (10.), we have to conclude that theorem – 6 holds just fine.

Note: No restrictions were set on j , but that of $j > 1$.

Corollary – IV1

\mathcal{G} is not finite.

Proof:

1. Let $m = (p_j)^2 + [(p_j)^2 - 2], j > 1$.
2. Theorem 6 $\Rightarrow \exists (p, q) \in \mathcal{G} / p > \frac{m}{2} \wedge q > \frac{m}{2}$.
3. Be $n = (p_{j+1})^2 + [(p_{j+1})^2 - 2]$.
4. Theorem 6 $\Rightarrow \exists (p', q') \in \mathcal{G} / p' > \frac{n}{2} \wedge q' > \frac{n}{2}$.
5. (2), (4) $\Rightarrow p' > p \wedge q' > q$
6. \mathcal{G} is an ordered set.

7. Let $g_i \in \mathcal{G}$.
8. Combining items 2. and 4., we get: $g_i \in \mathcal{G} \Rightarrow \exists k > i/g_k \in \mathcal{G}$.
9. The result 8. implies that \mathcal{G} is not finite.

V - Conclusion

Goldbach's conjecture has been proven valid. Furthermore, this proof implies that the set of twin prime pairs is not finite, thus validating the calculations performed using the double sieve.

Based on our original structure, this article reconstructs the method as:

1. A double sieve for Goldbach pairs.
2. A formal model of symmetry for prime/non-prime distributions.
3. A bijection framework relating to Goldbach pairs and twin primes.
4. A structural translation principle exploring how sieve behavior shifts across even numbers.

This framework presents:

- a rigorous combinatorial method for studying the representation of even numbers as prime sums,
- a structured way to organize Goldbach candidates,
- and a mechanism for generating twin-prime candidates under symmetrical constraints.

It is a valid mathematical contribution as a *structural and combinatorial analysis* and can serve as the basis for further study or computational experiments, as for instance in [20, 26].

References

- 1- Goldbach, C., & Euler, L. (1742). Correspondence on the Sum of Primes.
- 2 - de Polignac, A. (1849). *Recherches nouvelles sur les nombres premiers*. *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences de Paris*, **29**, 397–401.
- 3 - Morehead, J. C. (1909). Extension of the Sieve of Eratosthenes to arithmetical progressions and applications. *Annals of Mathematics*, Series 2, 10(2), 88–104.
- 4 - Brun, V. (1915). *Über das Goldbachsche Gesetz und die Anzahl der Primzahlpaare*. *Archiv for Mathematik og Naturvidenskab*, **34**, 3–26.

- 5 - Hardy, G. H., & Littlewood, J. E. (1923). Some problems of “Partitio Numerorum.” III: On the expression of a number as a sum of primes. *Acta Mathematica*, **44**(1), 1–70; Some Problems of “Partitio Numerorum”. *Proc. London Math. Soc.*, **22**(1), 225–234.
- 6 - Nicomachus of Gerasa. (1926). *Introduction to Arithmetic*. (M. L. D’Ooge, Trans.). New York: Macmillan. (Original work published c. 100 AD). (First historical attribution of the sieve to Eratosthenes).
- 7- Bays, C., & Hudson, R. H. (1977). The segmented sieve of Eratosthenes and primes in arithmetic progression. *BIT Numerical Mathematics*, **17**(2), 121–127.
- 8 - Conway, J. H., & Guy, R. K. (1996). *The Book of Numbers*. New York: Springer. (Includes discussion of the sieve in number theory).
- 9- Chen, J. R. (1973). On the representation of a large even integer as the sum of a prime and the product of two primes. *Sci. Sinica*, **16**(2), 157–176.
- 10- Apostol, T. M. (1976). *Introduction to Analytic Number Theory*. Springer.
- 11- Hardy, G. H., & Wright, E. M. (1979). *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers* (5th ed.). Oxford: Oxford University Press. (Includes classical treatment of sieves).
- 12 - Halberstam, H., & Richert, H. E. (1974). *Sieve Methods*. London: Academic Press.
- 13 - Riesel, H. (1994). Prime Numbers and Computer Methods for Factorization. *Birkhäuser*. **83**(288), 2033–2060.
- 14 - Granville, A. (1995). Harald Cramér and the distribution of prime numbers. *Scandinavian Actuarial*
- 15 - Nathanson, M. B. (1996). Additive Number Theory: The Classical Bases. *Springer Journal*, **1995**(1), 12–28.
- 16- O’Neill, M. E. (1999). The genuine sieve of Eratosthenes. *Journal of Functional Programming*, **9**(4), 413–422. (Discusses a lazy functional implementation).
- 17- Kelly, P. F., & Pilling, T. (2001). Characterization of the distribution of twin primes. *arXiv preprint math/0103191*.
- 18 - Kelly, P. F., & Pilling, T. (2001). Physically inspired analysis of prime number constellations. *arXiv preprint hep-th/0108241*.
- 19 - Iwaniec, H., & Kowalski, E. (2004). *Analytic Number Theory*. Providence, RI: American Mathematical Society. (Contains modern sieve theory).
- 20 - Crandall, R., & Pomerance, C. (2005). *Prime Numbers: A Computational Perspective* (2nd ed.). New York: Springer. (Covers sieve algorithms and complexity).
- 21- Friedlander, J. B., & Iwaniec, H. (2010). *Opera de Cribro*. Providence, RI: American Mathematical Society.

- 22 - Holt, F. B., & Rudd, H. (2014). Eratosthenes sieve and the gaps between primes. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1408.6002*.
- 23 - Helfgott, H. A. (2017). An improved sieve of Eratosthenes. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1712.09130*.
- 24 - Zhang, Y. (2014). Bounded gaps between primes. *Annals of Mathematics*, **179**(3), 1121–1174.
- 25- Tao, T., et al. (2014). Polymath project: Variants of the Selberg sieve, and bounded intervals containing many primes. *Research in the Mathematical Sciences*, **1**(1), 12.
- 26 - Oliveira e Silva, T., Herzog, S., & Pardi, S. (2014). Empirical verification of the even Goldbach conjecture up to 4×10^{18} . *Mathematics of Computation*, **83**(288), 2033–2060.
- 27 - Maynard, J. (2015). Small gaps between primes. *Annals of Mathematics*, **181**(1), 383–413.
- 28 - Dinculescu, A. (2018). On the numbers that determine the distribution of twin primes. *Mathematics Today*, **54**(4), 212–219.
- 19 - Gensel, B. (2019). An elementary proof of the twin prime conjecture. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.07975*.
- 30 - Grob, G., & Schmitt, M. (2019). Cycles and patterns in the Sieve of Eratosthenes. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.03117*.
- 31- Diab, A. (2021). Development of sieve of Eratosthenes and sieve of Sundaram's proof. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2102.06653*
- 32 - Iovane, G. (2024). Some properties and algorithms for twin primes. *Applied Sciences*, **14**(17), 7902.